

SIMILARITIES AND DIFFERENCES OF PROVERBS IN UZBEK AND ENGLISH FROM THE THEMATIC ASPECT

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7268626>

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Abstract : In this article, we focus on the linguistic and cultural characteristics of English and Uzbek proverbs, and the study of the thematic similarities and differences of proverbs in both languages will enrich this part of our work. In addition, we will try to express some unique features of the nation by introducing proverbs in both languages into a certain topic and finding alternative versions of proverbs related to this topic in both languages.

Key words: Proverbs, Uzbek folk proverbs, topic, in one place, alternatives, meaning;

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Received: 22-10-2022

Accepted: 22-10-2022

Published: 22-10-2022

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Based on the general meaning of proverbs, by dividing them into certain subject areas, we will bring out the characteristics of expression in proverbs, which are specific to the mentality of the English and Uzbek peoples. In this part, we will study all the relevant aspects of proverbs available in English and Uzbek languages. By doing a comparative analysis of proverbs that exist or do not occur in both languages, we will study the reasons why they exist or do not exist in the language.

Main part

Uzbek and English folk proverbs are very diverse in terms of subject matter. If we look at the collections of all Uzbek and English folk proverbs, we will see that in them, things and various events that occur in every aspect of the life of the Uzbek people are expressed in proverbs.

We will try to prove the reasons why proverbs on the same topic in the collection of "Uzbek folk proverbs" have alternative versions in both languages or not based on the mentality of the peoples.

No	Topic	English articulation	Uzbek translation	Uzbek alternative version
1	Vatan va vatanparvarlik	Every bird likes its own nest.	Har bir qush o'z inini sevadi.	Bulbul chamanni sevar-Odam Vatanni.
2	Mehnatsevarlik	Speak less	Ko'p gapirma,	Qo'ling

	va ishyoqmaslik	but do more.	ko'p ishla.	ishda, ko'ngling Allohda bo'lsin
3	Halollik va tekinxo'rlik	Back is spent under his belly, What is got over the devil's	Shayton kuchi bilan topilgan, shayton puchi bilan ketar	Haromdan yig'ilgan haromga ketar
4	To'g'rilik va egrilik	Ill gotten, ill spent.	Yomonlik bilan topilgan yomonlikka ketar.	Haromdan kelgan haromga ketar.
5	Yaxshilik va yomonlik	Forgive and forget.	Kechir va unut.	Yomonlikni yaxshilik bilan yeng.

Almost all proverbs related to all topics found in Uzbek folk proverbs can be found in English folk proverbs. As a proof of our opinion, we have tried to search for and cite the alternative versions of proverbs of all subjects found in Uzbek folk proverbs in English or Uzbek proverbs found in English folk proverbs.

So, in Uzbek and English folk proverbs, it is possible to find equivalents of proverbs that are similar in terms of subject. As a result, do not take a proverb on any topic, it has its alternative in both languages. The main reason for this is that all human characteristics are characteristic of all nations. However, with these thoughts, we cannot give the opinion that Uzbek and English proverbs have exactly the same meaning. We just want to find out whether the topics found in English and Uzbek proverbs are present in proverbs in both languages.

If we analyze the proverbs separately, we can see that their meaning is not the same in all of them. But based on the main purpose of this part of our article, we do not want to analyze the versions of proverbs in both languages. Importantly, we proved that proverbs on a certain topic in English can also be found in Uzbek, or vice versa, proverbs on a certain topic in Uzbek can also be found in English.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we can say that according to our research on English and Uzbek proverbs, we can find all the topics found in Uzbek proverbs in English proverbs. Some of them have similarities and some have no similarities at all.

REFERENCES:

1. Imamov K., Mirzayev T., Sarimsakov B., Safarov O. Uzbek folk oral poetic creation. -T.: Teacher, 1990.- 303b.
2. Berdieva Mukarrama Anvarovna, Bazarova Shohida Ashirkulovna Lexical And Grammatical Features Of The Compilation Of The RCT Textbook . *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(05), 429-431.
3. Karamatova K.M., Karamatov H.S. Proverbs - Ploclost. - T.: Labor, -2000.- 398 p.

4. Bazarova Shohida Ashirkulovna. Methodology of teaching the russian language in higher education. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali. 2022

5. Bazarova Shohida Ashirkulovna. Methodology of teaching the russian language in higher education/ O'ZBEKISTONDA FANLARARO INNOVATSIYALAR VA ILMIY TADQIQOTLAR JURNALI

4. Marvin, D.E. Antiquity of Proverbs. - New York and London: GP Putnam Sons, 1922-103 p.

5. Turakulovna Y. F., Ashirkulovna B. SH. Pedagogical Communication and its Importance //Journal of Pedagogical Inventions and Practices. -2022. -T. 6. -C. 21-22.

6. Berdiyeva M.A., Bazarova Sh.A. The role of authentic materials in teaching Russian language in higher education / Molodoy ucheniy. – 2022. – № 17 (412). – S. 288-289. – URL: <https://moluch.ru/archive/412/90852/> 12.08.2022).